

Why Everyone Must Write

Mohammed Zafar Khan

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Introduction

Have you wondered what a book really is? We know that a book is a bunch of pages stitched together and protected by a cover. It is often called a medium for recording information. Everything we know about our world today is because someone decided to record and retain information gathered through their personal experience(s).

The Art of Counting

The oldest form of writing known to historians and scientists is actually a method of counting. Counting by making marks or cutting notches into bones; these bones are assumed to be roughly 37,000 years old.

We've made and used basic tools out of stones and quartz for over two million years. We think language first evolved around 50,000–150,000 years ago, which is around the same time modern humans evolved.

We do not know exactly when and how humans developed the ability to count. Our best guess suggests that humans were counting as far back as 50,000 years ago. What we know for sure, though, is this: we had the necessity to count before we developed the need to communicate.

Communication is a Necessity

There's a reason they say "Necessity is the mother of all inventions." One such necessity for us humans was communication. We understood somehow that whatever was going on in our head must be shared with another human for the collective benefit of both parties involved, or a group of people, or probably even the human race.

It became absolutely necessary to find ways and means to communicate with one another to help one another hunt better, become aware of predators, and defend ourselves, among other things.

Language Development

We already knew the art of counting, and if I could point my finger at myself and count myself as 1, I'd point the same finger at you and count you as 2, and someone else as 3, and so on. Now, all I have to do is make a sound for "ME" and make a slightly different sound for "YOU."

Now we have the most basic structure needed to develop a language: numbers, reference, and sound. In this case, a finger pointing at oneself or someone else is the reference.

But this doesn't always work, as I cannot talk about person 2 & 3 with person 4 without both 2 & 3 being present because I have nobody to point at. Likewise, I cannot warn someone about a danger or a new predator that I saw yesterday because, to do that, I need to create new references that denote a threat and the concept of time.

At the simplest level, I need to be able to define something as 'safe' or 'dangerous', 'edible' or 'non-edible', clear differentiation between things such as boulders and trees, and I need to be able to explain the concept of time, mainly the difference between yesterday and today.

Why yesterday and today and why not tomorrow? As early humans, we probably never worried about tomorrow. Worrying about tomorrow is a recent development in human evolution.

I already have the tools that I would use to scrape markings into bones, wood, and stones. I would teach my fellow primitive humans the meaning of these markings fairly easily, and they would repeat the process of mirroring these markings to remember the symbol, character, or letter and the reference associated with it.

For example, let's say I want to carve a symbol that signifies a snake. Snake is a threat; it looks a certain way as it crawls on the ground, so I might make a simple "S" to represent a crawling snake. I may associate the "hiss" sound with this marking to further clarify it, and I might add lines or dots above or below the symbol to indicate if it's a threat or not.

What I explained here is how I think we developed language over a period of roughly 150,000 years.

The ability to amalgamate a set of sounds associated with markings or letters into words that 'mean' something is humankind's most beautiful invention for communicating, collecting, storing, retrieving, manipulating, and disseminating information.

Math of Language

If we don't know "how many" different sounds exist or can be produced by our vocal cords, we won't be able to learn any language or develop the ability to communicate with others. Therefore, the "how many" is a number.

This means, before we can understand sounds and letters, we need to understand the concept of counting 1... 2... 3... 4... and only then can we learn to vocalize different sounds. Numbers and sounds have always been equally (if not more) important than inscriptions in the development of every language.

Even to this day after six million years of evolution, we teach our young to count before we teach them sounds like A, B, C, after which we teach them to write these letters.

Our modern-day tools, a chalk and a blackboard, have replaced the paleolithic tools made of stones, wood, and bones, but the concept of language development to this day remains the same.

The Art of Storytelling

The more you develop the ability to create new references about new things, the better you can share and communicate with others. If you don't know what to call something, you cannot talk about it.

Imagine you are a cave(wo)man, and you want to share a story with your fellow humans about how a lion attacked you last night and how you managed to save yourself and lived to tell the tale. You need to have the ability to describe the situation in as much detail as possible.

You might feel the necessity to mention how dark the night was or how bright the moon in the sky looked. These details help your listeners understand the story, and they could possibly imagine and experience the whole incident just the way you did, without even being there; that is the power of communication.

Greatest Human Desire

At some point, our simple communications evolved into complex storytelling, and with that came the need to preserve our stories. The more details we add, the lengthier our story gets, which makes it difficult to remember it with all its details intact.

The deepest human desire has been debated over by philosophers for thousands of years. Sigmund Freud said the greatest human desire is the "desire to be great," i.e., to feel that one is an important figure in this world, to be known by everyone, and to be remembered throughout history.

Some have argued that immortality is the great human desire, and some say finding our purpose or meaning or God is our greatest desire, but I disagree with all of them.

Like everything else, the deepest human desire has also developed through the process of evolution. The deepest and greatest desire of a single-cell organism was to split into two, and those two into four. It may sound like immortality, but it really isn't.

The cells aren't trying to live forever; they are trying to leave a tiny trace of themselves behind before they die or split into two, and the same is true for us humans too. We are, in so many ways, exactly like single-cell organisms. All we are trying to do is leave a tiny trace of ourselves behind before we die. We reproduce to leave a trace of our genes and tell stories to leave a trace of our lives behind us after we are gone.

The History of Writing

In the 19th century, a young Spanish archaeologist named Marcelino Sanz de Sautuola went to the Altamira Cave in northern Spain, where he found some prehistoric parietal art. They are now known as one of the oldest and amongst the best-preserved cave-paintings worldwide.

This cave art is estimated to be at least 35,600 years old. Which means, for over 35,000 years, humans have known how important it is to preserve stories, hence giving birth to something we now call our recorded history.

History repeats itself in more ways than we know or understand it. Who would have thought thirty-five thousand years ago that one day, someone would discover it in a cave, that one day it would be on every major newspaper's front page?

The artist of the painting could have never imagined a 35,000-year timeline or comprehended how his/her act of painting charcoal and ochre images of handprints, bison, and horses would be a matter of intellectual discussions for over two centuries and counting.

The artist would have never thought back then that I'd be writing about his or her art in my book and so many of you would be reading about it.

But why did the caveman paint on cave walls? Well, when the caveman learned how to paint and species later on learned to write, they had plenty to say. I'm sure they used animal skin to record their stories but quickly learned it's probably not a good idea to preserve history on biodegradable material; stone was their obvious best choice. It must have taken them 20,000 years or so to go from paintings in caves to engraving symbols into stone tablets.

About 10,000 years ago, we went from being hunter-gatherers to agriculture, producing our own food. We domesticated animals and cultivated cereal grains.

5,000 years ago, we stepped into the Bronze Age; we learned the art of working with metals, made a copper and tin alloy, and named it bronze. Bronze tools made cutting down trees faster, helping us to build great cities.

Ancient Egyptians built their pyramids during the Bronze Age, and the earliest writings, such as the Egyptian hieroglyphs and petroglyph engravings on rock, also come from this era.

Roughly 3,000 years ago (900 B.C.), after the Bronze Age, we discovered the knack of heating and forging iron, marking the beginning of the Iron Age. With the discovery of iron, everything from agriculture to art and organized religion became more sophisticated, and so did writing, written documentation, cultures, and languages.

Why Everyone Must Write

The Etruscan Gold Book, made from six sheets of twenty-four-carat gold bound together with rings and estimated to be 2,673 years old, has Etruscan characters, a horse, a horseman, a Siren, a lyre, and soldiers. It is thought to be the oldest multi-page book in the world. This book is evidence that around 3,000 years ago, we realized we wouldn't be remembered by our wealth or material possessions, but rather by our achievements, conquests, and good or bad deeds—and the only way to preserve all of it is through storytelling.

Whether it was Moses or Mahatma Gandhi, Mother Teresa or Martin Luther King, Nelson Mandela or Adolf Hitler, Karl Marx or George W. Bush, today we know about them and understand the events of history thanks to the art of storytelling. We've preserved their achievements, their deeds, and most importantly, their stories in our books.

If Einstein hadn't put $E = mc^2$ on paper and had this idea only lived in his head, history would be quite different. Of course, someone else would have eventually figured it out one

way or another, but that would have simply created a different historical timeline altogether.

In the 1960s, writers Cornbread and Cool Earl went around towns of Philadelphia, spray painting their names on walls to gain attention from the community and media. We now call this form of art "graffiti."

But graffiti didn't start in the 1960s; it started way back. From the oldest cave paintings to modern-day graffiti, it has come a long way and seems to have always influenced the course of history. Thanks to the Greeks and Romans for giving birth to democracy by simply writing their names and protest poems on the walls of ancient buildings and iconic monuments.

My point is, preserving and sharing our theories, ideas, and ideologies with the world changes the world a tiny bit, and that tiny bit over time creates a butterfly effect and changes history forever.

My objective in writing this article is to pass on a remarkably simple and clear message to the world, and that is, **EVERYONE MUST WRITE**.

References

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- [2] Smith, J. (2008). *The Etruscan Gold Book and Ancient Writing*. *Archaeology Journal*, 72(3), 45-52.